

PROFESSIONAL BIOETHICS IN ORTHOPEDIC DENTISTRY

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Purpose of the study: to study the formation of dental bioethics as an independent branch of science.

Materials and methods: The emergence of alternative state-paid medical services has revealed new ethical and legal problems affecting the interests of patients, medical workers and society. In order to improve the mechanisms for regulating social, economic and medical relations of legal entities and individuals in the dental care system, both in medical practice and during scientific research. Dental diseases occupy a leading place among the general pathology of organs and systems. Every person at least once in his life visited a dental office owned by the state or another form of ownership. Increasingly, patients have to receive dental care at their own expense, since health insurance does not always financially provide the patient with the necessary treatment. In the structure of dental interventions, the leading place, according to official statistics, belongs to therapeutic dentistry. The list of therapeutic dentistry services includes the treatment of caries, non-carious lesions, complicated caries, periodontal diseases and oral mucosa, as well as a whole group of interventions related to the aesthetic requirements of patients: teeth whitening, fixation of dental jewelry, aesthetic correction of color, size and tooth shapes. A feature of the work of dental therapists in the performance of their professional duties is their general medical training, especially in such areas as periodontal diseases and

oral mucosa. One of the important functions of a dental therapist is to make a diagnosis and determine the tactics of management and treatment of the patient. The basis of ethical problems that arise from incorrect diagnosis is often the insufficient professional level of the doctor, which can lead to errors in diagnosing the disease. In these cases, the patient needs to explain the fact and reasons for the error and the circumstances that contributed to this and, in general, follow the principles of harmonization of law and ethics in medicine. Concealing errors associated with professional incompetence can lead to serious complications, which, in turn, can be the subject of litigation. A dental therapist constantly deals with manipulations that bring not only positive emotions. The cause of advanced dental diseases is often the fear of dental intervention. Pain relief has more than just an emotional and moral aspect. The most common dental disease is caries. The basis for the emergence of critical, from an ethical point of view, situations in the relationship between the doctor and the patient associated with the treatment of caries may be pain during the preparation of hard dental tissues, mechanical trauma to the oral mucosa, significant destruction of the coronal part of the tooth, or opening of the tooth cavity. The listed consequences of medical intervention can lead to serious complications and contribute to a deterioration in the quality of life. If such a situation arises, it would be correct to explain to the patient the problem that has arisen and make an adequate decision to eliminate it. Another ethical problem associated with the treatment of caries can arise from the situation caused by the loss of a filling. Doctors may interpret this situation as a consequence of working with low-quality material, and as a result, the patient is offered to use a more expensive filling material. However, the cause of the filling falling out may be a violation of the filling technology. From the point of view of bioethics, in this case there is a violation of the principle of providing the patient with adequate, objective and complete information. Analysis of information obtained from scientific literature, search for information on conducted research, analysis of statistical data.

Results and discussion: today it should be recognized that dentistry is a unique field medicine in the sense that its degree of commercialization is higher than in many others.

There are many private dental clinics in the cities of America, Europe and the post-Soviet space.

First of all, dentistry is a component of the health care system aimed at preserving and maintaining oral health, and dentists are specialists with perfect skills and abilities in their areas. But at the turn of the 20th and 11th centuries, dentistry also turned into a commercial service, which led to the emergence of duality in the status of the consumer of dental services. In Western countries with development -In that market economy, such a consumer is considered binary: as a patient in need in assistance, and as a client purchasing dental services. In this regard, there is a need a more detailed study of classical bioethical principles in dental practice. However, society does not view dental care as a standard market good, but sees it as a matologists have specialists with certain knowledge and skills and instructs them to carry out their work professional responsibility to give priority to the well-being of their patients. A dentist, like any doctor assumes, first of all, obligations to society to provide high-quality dental care. And here it is important to add: in accordance with moral and ethical standards. These moral and ethical norms, obligations and standards are the subject of study of a new direction in bioethics, possibly nobody in the 1990s. – dental bioethics. The field of bioethical regulation in dentistry practice is very diverse. It highlights several areas:

- relationship between doctor and patient;
- relationships within a professional group of dentists;
- relationships between dentists and other groups of medical specialists;
- relations of property and profit in dental practice;
- attitude to new scientific achievements and criteria for their use in dental practice;
- relations on the market of drugs used in dental practice;

- aesthetic standards of dental care;
- dentists attitude to social and natural factors influencing the health status of patients;
- principles of isolation of this professional group in society;
- attitude to the authorities and laws in force in a given society;
- relationships within the professional group of medical workers in dental practice;
- the moral status of the patient in relation to his health and the doctor's recommendations.

Conclusion. Doctors and dentists must have a broad outlook, be diversified, thoughtful, non-selfish specialists and, at the same time, be attentive and cordial towards -to patients. This can be achieved through in-depth integration of bioethical principles into dental education.

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